
HOLONIC EXECUTION SYSTEM FOR SKILL-BASED RECONFIGURABLE CYBER-PHYSICAL PRODUCTION MODULES

Aleksandr Sidorenko, Achim Wagner

Deutsches Forschungszentrum für Künstliche Intelligenz GmbH (DFKI)
Trippstadter Strasse 122, 67663 Kaiserslautern, Germany
{Aleksandr Sidorenko}aleksandr.sidorenko@dfki.de

Martin Ruskowski

Deutsches Forschungszentrum für Künstliche Intelligenz GmbH (DFKI)
Trippstadter Strasse 122, 67663 Kaiserslautern, Germany
Institute of machine tools and control systems (WSKL)
University of Kaiserslautern-Landau, 67663 Kaiserslautern, Germany

ABSTRACT

Reconfigurable cyber-physical production modules (RCPPMs) can become the backbone of the future cyber-physical production systems (CPPSs) by enabling rapid adaptation responses to changing conditions at the machine's level. One of the challenges to developing such machines is the lack of control architectures that can provide the required levels of modularity and reconfigurability while remaining reliable and safe. The skill-based design improves the flexibility of the software, but to enable adaptation, automatic composition of skills is required. Holonic architectures have shown a great potential for building reconfigurable manufacturing systems (RMS), though they focus mostly on the MES level and product logistics. This paper proposes a holonic execution system for the skill-based RCPPMs. It integrates the ARTI reference architecture with the skill's composition framework, which utilizes the so-called distributed behavior trees (DBTs) and the actor-based software design. We also demonstrate how the ARTI holons relate to the concepts of Industry 4.0. The proposed approach aims to enable automatic composition of skills for the RCPPMs.

Keywords holonic execution system · skill-based reconfigurable cyber-physical production modules · automatic skills' composition · actor-based design · ARTI reference architecture

1 Introduction

To enable the transition to mass customization and personalized production, Industry 4.0 envisions a new generation of interconnected and flexible cyber-physical production systems (CPPSs). One of the unique features of CPPSs is their *adaptability*, which requires a system to adapt both its behavior and structure to changing conditions [1]. Reconfigurable cyber-physical production modules (RCPPMs) can become the backbone of such systems by enabling the required levels of reconfigurability and intelligence on the machine level and lowering the overall number of machines on the production floor. One of the challenges to developing such machines is designing a control system that is modular and flexible enough to enable a high level of reconfigurability without sacrificing safety or real-time requirements.

The skill-based engineering helps to increase the reconfiguration potential of the RMS by decoupling the required production processes from those that are executed on production resources, and encapsulating machine-specific functions behind standard interfaces [2]. Currently, the skill-oriented design mostly targets the MES level of the factory control. Skills provided by the production modules are complex, universal, and reusable. Skills' composition inside the machines is mostly manual. The real-time requirements to the control software are kept encapsulated in the skills, behind the interface. To enable rapid and autonomous reconfiguration, an automatic composition of skills is required. Moreover, as the control software runs at the intra-module level, the real-time requirements must also be respected. Holonic

manufacturing systems (HMS) have shown their great potential for adaptability, but, as the skill-oriented designs, they also focus on MES level and product logistics.

In our previous work [3], we have defined a formal framework for skills' composition that utilizes a distributed behavior trees (BTs) model. In this paper, we propose an implementation of our framework using a holonic execution system (HES) based on the ARTI reference architecture. We provide a unifying view on skill-based and holonic approaches to designing control software for RCPPMs. The combination of these two approaches brings several advantages. First, the HES serves as a layer of intelligence for skills and enables their self-composition. Second, the distributed BTs provide the semi-heterarchical structure to the ARTI's activity holons, which adds more efficiency and real-time capabilities to the intra-machine control systems. We also show how the ARTI holons relate to and can be integrated with the concepts of Industry 4.0, such as Asset Administration Shells (AAS), to increase their interoperability in the I4.0 ecosystem.

The paper is structured in the following way. section 2 gives a short overview of the relevant approaches to support reconfigurability in production systems. In section 3 we briefly describe the base models, which we use in our skills' composition framework. section 4 proposes the ARTI-based holonic execution system for the framework, described in section 3. Finally, in section 5 we discuss the proposed approach.

2 Related Works

2.1 Skill-based Engineering in Manufacturing and Robotics

Froschauer et al. in [4] have listed the expected benefits of using skills in manufacturing, such as flexibility and planning efficiency in production, development efficiency, reuse, and interoperability. Koecher et al. in [5] have provided a reference model for a common understanding of skills, capabilities, and services in manufacturing. By explicitly separating capabilities from skills, it is possible to decouple the description of a function from its implementation. In the previous years, several prototypes have shown the applicability and benefits of using skill-based design for modular, plug-and-produce capable production systems [6, 7]. Dorofeev has proposed a holistic approach for skill-based engineering in the industrial automation domain [2]. The author stresses the relation of skills to services from service-oriented architectures (SOA) and focuses on the skills' orchestration. In robotics, skill-based design focuses on reusability, modularity, and role separation. Skills are reusable components that encapsulate expert knowledge in some task, e.g., in trajectory planning. Skills typically reside on the lower levels of a multilayer architecture, as in [8], and are used by a sequencing layer to automatically build complex robot's behaviors. Rovida et al. have defined a robot skill as a fundamental software block, which changes the world state [9].

2.2 Behavior Trees in Automation

Behavior trees (BTs) as a supervisory control framework has got recently attention in the robotics and the artificial intelligence communities. The authors in [10] have formalized BTs' model to analyze such properties as robustness, efficiency, and safety. A detailed survey of BTs research and applications is presented in [11]. The authors in [12] have proposed to augment BTs with the dataflow notation of their coordination language, Lingua Franca, for developing concurrent, distributed real-time systems. [13] has proposed an approach to enhance the modularity of the industrial control software by integrating BTs into PLC programs and separating hardware-related functionalities from the coordination logic, which is subject to frequent changes during reconfiguration. The authors argue that the approach improves the skill-based programming approach for PLCs by using BTs for skill composition. To deal with the software modularity and distributed character of the control system in RCPPMs, the authors in [3] have proposed to use Behavior Trees (BTs) as a modular supervisory framework for skills' composition and execution.

2.3 Agents and holons for the RCPPMs

A cyber-physical production module (CPPM) typically consists of a set of actuators and sensors that interact with the environment, a computation platform, and a software layer that controls its hardware and provides the interfaces for the external users [1]. The skill-based CPPMs implement their production functions as the so-called skills with the standardized interface and behavior, and describe them as the module's capabilities. As part of the Industry 4.0 ecosystem, a CPPM has its standard digital representation in the form of the AAS that equips the module with the self-description capabilities. In the holonic CPPMs, a resource holon takes care of the module's management and enables flexible production planning and execution through collaboration, e.g., through the use of the auction-based distributed scheduling protocol, as in [14] or [15]. The resource holon serves as a proactive entity and uses the standard skill interface to control the module's hardware, as well as the AAS's API to get the information for self-configuration. More details about the holonic intelligent CPPMs can be found in [16] and [17]. A bio-inspired online scheduling approach is called a *delegate-MAS* (D-MAS) from [18]. It uses the lightweight agents, called ants, for looking ahead

and evaluating different production possibilities before the actual resource allocation happens. Leitão et al. in [14] have proposed to use Petri Nets (PN) to formally model the behaviors of each holon to enable the analysis and formal validation.

An RCPPM has an aggregated structure, and its functionality depends on the modules that comprise its current topology. One of the challenges is that it must be able to integrate new, unknown modules and adapt its functionality accordingly. The ARTI's approach [18] of executing activities on resources addresses this requirement and aligns well with the skill-based design for the RCPPMs. Capabilities and composite skills can be considered the ARTI's activity holons. The atomic skills provided by CPPMs naturally fit the ARTI's resource instance holons. However, the ARTI's heterarchical architecture may require many interactions between holons during task execution. This may not be as critical on the MES level, but it affects the real-time execution requirements of the RCPPMs.

3 Skills Composition Framework

This section briefly describes the main concepts and models that we use for skill's composition in the RCPPMs. Further details can be found in [3]. The base assumption is that different components inside a production module provide a set of parametrizable controllers, which, given the right set of narrow conditions, guarantee to complete their task successfully. A system can intelligently give control to one or more of these controllers to produce the required behavior. The process of choosing the right controllers is decoupled from the low-level control policies and can be done automatically to support the module's new topology. These controllers are represented by the so-called skills that provide the standard interface needed for their parametrization and composition. In addition, skills offer the mechanism of pre- and postconditions to facilitate the development of the composition strategy.

The skills' composition framework that has been formally defined in [3] is based on the behavior trees (BTs). The detailed and formal definition of BTs can be found in [10]. A BT is a control structure that encodes an agent's behavior by mapping the environment states to the agent's actions. BTs are self-similar and recursive. Each subtree can be treated simultaneously as a tree to its child nodes and as an action node to its parent tree. This makes BTs conceptually close to holons, as each BT on every hierarchy level can be considered a holon. BTs encode abstraction levels and priorities in their structure, where the more abstract behaviors are located at the top of the tree and the priority levels go from the left to the right under the control flow nodes. All subtrees share the same basic interface, which enhances modularity and simplifies the composition of control structures.

In [3] we showed that a skill can be modeled as a BT with a specific structure, which is called a **precondition-postcondition-invariant-action** (PPIA) and is shown in Figure 1 (for an example, see *Skill_1*). The following considerations have motivated this structure. A device's controller implies some constraints on the environment to guarantee its success. There must be some starting conditions, or *preconditions*, when the controller can be activated. Additionally, some conditions from those preconditions must always hold true when the controller is executing. These conditions can represent some safety constraints or the results of the running task, which have been previously achieved. Such conditions can be called *invariants*. The state of the system after the controller successfully finishes its task can be described by the controller's actions' effects, or *postconditions*.

By modeling skills as BTs we can automatically compose them into more complex, composite skills using the technique called **backchaining of BTs**. The backchaining of BTs was first proposed in [19]. The approach is based on the two main ideas: first, creating an atomic BT for each action template in the PPIA-form; second, iteratively replacing failed conditions with the atomic BTs, which work to make the failed conditions succeed. The principle is shown in the upper part of Figure 1. A task is presented as a sequence composition of conditions (C_1, C_2, C_3) , which represent the required effect after task completion. Now, assuming that a set of skills has been implemented and registered in the system, the task is to iteratively find those skills that can achieve these conditions. For example, the $Skill_1$ ensures the condition C_1 if its postcondition is the same, i.e., $S_{Skill_1} \subset S_{C_1}$ (S is success region). There might be several skills that satisfy the required condition C_1 ($Skill_1$ and $Skill_2$). We can compose such skills using a fallback operator and replace the condition C_1 in the sequence by the resulting BT. This makes the resulting control strategy more robust to disturbances, as if the $Skill_1$ fails, the $Skill_2$ tries to achieve the condition C_1 . If a precondition of a skill fails, e.g., C_{pre}^3 of the $Skill_3$, then we can try to find another skill with the same postcondition $C_{post}^{3,1}$ of the $Skill_{3,1}$ and replace the failed condition with this skill.

As the RCPPMs are modular and consist of various networked cyber-physical components running concurrently, we can compose concurrently running processes using the approach proposed by Johannes Reich in [20]. Reich proposes to divide the composition of interactive systems into external and internal. The external composition takes place when so-called interaction partitions of each process communicate with each other through protocols. By internal composition, Reich means the coordination of different roles inside each component. Composed this way, computation processes form a so-called **snowflake** topology without any cycles (the lower part of the Figure 1).

Figure 1: Skills Composition Framework proposed in [3].

To complete our skills' composition framework, we combine our skill model with the model proposed by Reich in [20] in the following way. If BTs are running on separate components or in separate threads of control concurrently, they are composed using the external composition by protocols. As the BTs model enforces the use of one interface across all its nodes, we need only one protocol, which has been defined in [21]. For the BTs running locally on one computation resource, we can use the composition rules defined by the BTs framework. The internal composition of the interface state machines is done by a BT running inside a computational process. For more details, please check the [3].

4 Holonic execution system for the skill-based RCPPMs

In this section, we propose an ARTI-based holonic execution system for the skill-based RCPPMs and show how the ARTI principles supported by the Industry 4.0 concepts can be used to automatically build composite skills during the reconfiguration of the RCPPMs. Firstly, we discuss how the ARTI’s holons can fit into the skill-based RCPPMs. Secondly, we draft an approach to skills’ self-composition using ARTI’s D-MASs.

4.1 ARTI Holons for RCPPMs

The ARTI reference architecture is “... a holonic reference architecture for execution systems managing real-world activities using real-world resources.” [18] The ARTI’s approach of executing activities on resources aligns well with the skill-based design for CPPMs. In this section, we investigate how the ARTI holons relate to the concepts of capabilities and skills and how these two approaches can be combined to automatically build composite skills during the reconfiguration of the RCPPMs. The information about the ARTI concepts provided in this section is mostly taken from [18]. The concepts of capabilities and skills are aligned with the CSS-model from [5].

Figure 2: ARTI Holons for the RCPPMs.

An *Activity Type holon (AT-holon)* “... corresponds to a class of real-world activities [18].” It has and provides expert knowledge about the activities of this type. In the CSS-model [5], such activities, or automation functions, are described by the so-called capabilities, which can be modeled as knowledge graphs or defined as a *Capability* element of an AAS. Since a capability is just a passive description of a function, an AT-holon can actively provide the required information by either using the corresponding knowledge graph or the AAS submodel. This aligns well with the ARTI’s concept of the *intelligent beings*, which provide an accurate image of the world of interest, and the *intelligent agents*, which act proactive and provide intelligence [18]. In production, driven by products, such as in [15], a Product AAS holds product models, process plans, material requirements, as well as capabilities required to produce a product. The AT-holon

can use the *Capabilities* submodel of the Product AAS. On the other hand, as envisioned in [22], with the dawn of an internet of activities executing on an internet of things, complex activities may probably have their own AASs.

A **Resource Type holon (RT-holon)** "... corresponds to a class of real-world resources." [18] It provides all the information about resource instances of its type. In the context of CPPS, resources are production modules, transport systems, intelligent components taking part in production, or even smart workers [16]. Since all the information about a resource can be reached through its AAS, the RT-holon, similar to the AT-holon, serves as an active part of the AAS. It negotiates with the AT-holons regarding the capability of its resource to provide the required type of functionality. The CSS-model separates the capabilities required to produce a product from those that are provided by the resources available in production. The so-called matching of these capabilities can be done through the interactions between the AT- and RT-holons. Though in the ARTI architecture, the particular algorithms for decision-making are used as the system plugins and are decoupled from the system by the holons. As capability matching is a broad research topic in the skill-based engineering community, it has been left out of scope in this paper.

A **Resource Instance holon (RI-holon)** "... corresponds to a real-world instance of a resource, which is valuable and has a finite capacity. [18]" It handles all the instance-specific information and allocates its resource to perform the required activities. The RI-holon is analogous to the resource holon from [17]. It provides management functions and holds the module's state. The difference to [17] is that the RI-holon does not control the module's hardware through its skills but rather parametrizes and manages access to them by maintaining the local schedule, or agenda. It delegates the execution of skills to the so-called actors, which will be described later in the section. This allows for simultaneous execution of multiple skills, as well as skill preemption.

An **Activity Instance holon (AI-holon)** "... corresponds to the execution of a real-world activity [18]." It ensures the necessary allocation of the resource instances and also holds the information about the current state of the execution. In production systems, there is an activity instance for each product manufacturing activity. In [17] this task is handled by the **Product holon**. As in production there might be all sorts of activities, which are not directly connected with the process of a product manufacturing, e.g., maintenance or other auxiliary functions, the AI-holon generalizes the Product holons. In the skill-based RCPs, the AI-holon represents a composite skill that implements this activity, and manages its execution. When building a composite skill, the major task is to find and allocate the required resources, as well as to build and parametrize the BT, which encodes the required skill. The AI-holon also keeps track of its activity's state, and the BT, being mostly memoryless, uses this knowledge to properly react. To be able to manage execution of various activities, the AI-holon must be agnostic to the task domain it currently manages. For this, it fully relies on the information it gets from its AT-holon.

4.2 Actors D-MAS for Automatic Skills Composition and Execution

In the ARTI architecture, the tasks of searching and allocating resources capable of executing actions are delegated to the so-called *delegate MASs* (D-MASs), such as the so-called the exploration and the intention-propagation D-MASs. Without such D-MASs the ARTI implementations would be heterarchical control systems. The rationale behind this design is to facilitate looking ahead and dynamic scheduling in changeable production environments [18]. For the intra-machine control we propose to use an additional D-MAS, which can be called an **actor D-MAS**, as it has been inspired by an actor-oriented design from [23]. The motivation behind this decision is justified by the real-time requirements and the necessity to run skills on various, often resource constrained hardware.

The D-MAS is an architectural pattern that allows a holon to delegate some of its responsibilities to a swarm of lightweight agents [18]. Several D-MASs have been developed in the scope of the ARTI architecture, the *exploration* and *intention-propagation D-MASs* being the most prominent ones. These D-MASs utilize the bio-inspired principles from the food-foraging ants. The exploration D-MAS is used for the decentralized search of resources capable of executing the required actions. This approach can also be employed for the capability matching task in the skill-based production. The intention-propagation D-MAS is in essence a decentralized scheduling technique. More details on the these and some other D-MASs can be found in [18].

The idea standing behind the proposed actor D-MAS is that instead of the step-by-step execution of actions by the AI-holon, a network of actors that represent a distributed behavior tree (DBT), as described in section 3, is generated automatically through the interactions between the ARTI holons. This DBT is in essence a grounded composite skill, meaning that it is connected to the required hardware, parametrized, and ready to be executed when the time comes. This can be considered as an approach to multiresource allocation.

In [19] the authors propose to create the BT iteratively by executing it. This may be beneficial for a robot acting in an unknown environment. For the production modules, such an approach may not be feasible. First, because the resulting BT may have conflicts between its actions and requires some convergence analysis, as described in [10]. Second, as the BT will directly control the physical system, it is prudent to have some assurances of correctness before letting it do

it. This amplifies the central role of digital twins in the (re-)configuration process of the RCPPMs, as the iteratively synthesized BT will be first executed virtually, or simulated.

A basis for the actor D-MAS is drawn from an actor-oriented design, which has been suggested by Lee et al. in [23] and is particularly suitable for modeling concurrently running computational processes typical for cyber-physical systems. Very broadly, actors are components that execute concurrently and communicate with each other through some messaging mechanism via explicit communication channels. Actors have a well-defined interface, which includes ports as the actor’s communication points and parameters to configure an actor. As this design is abstract, it can be implemented by technologies from different domains: the distributed control model of the IEC61499 standard from industrial automation, the nodes model of the Robot Operating System (ROS) from the robotics domain, or the agent-oriented design from distributed AI.

Figure 3: Block diagram of the composite skill formed by the actor D-MAS.

Figure 3 shows a block diagram of the actors D-MAS representing a part of the BT ($Skill_1$ and $Skill_2$) in Figure 1. Actors of the D-MAS can be spawned by both AI- and RI-holons and come in several forms:

- **RI-actors** are spawned by the RI-holon normally in the execution environment where a resource (a sensor or an actuator) resides. They represent the leaves of the behavior tree. This can be either a parameterized instance of the atomic skill itself or a skill’s requester, which knows how to interact with this skill. This is done because each resource may have its unique native cyber-layer, and the RI-holon actor serves as an adapter between the resource’s native interface and the standard interface of the BT.
- **AI-actors** are spawned by the AI-holon and form a coordination logic of the composite skill. They represent the BT’s control nodes, are hardware and domain-agnostic, and can be generically generated (see the Fallback AI-actor. The $\ll BT \gg$ stereotype means that the actor complies with the BTSync protocol and can be treated as a BT node).
- **Connector-actors** build the communication channels between the actors. They can be spawned by both AI- and RI-holons. In the simplest case, they are just the virtual links between the actors, which reside in the same execution platform. The goal is, on the one hand, to decouple the actors from each other, on the other, to

enforce the topology described in [20]. These actors effectively serve as routers both for the control signals, defined by the BTSync protocol [3], and for the data between the output and the input ports of the actors.

- **Adaptor-actors** are the specialization of the connector-actors. Their goal is to adapt different communication or interaction protocols if the actors of the BT are executed on the different computational platforms. The adaptor-actors are spawned by the respective RI-holons representing the specific channels, as they are treated as the resources. The information needed for self-configuration of the communication channels is taken from the respective submodels of the resources' AASs.

Though not in the scope of this paper, it is worth mentioning that to enable self-organizing properties, the actors may provide the so-called evaporate-and-refresh services, or digital pheromones, analogous to [18] and [14]. These pheromones must be refreshed at regular intervals or the network of the actors breaks apart, actors die, and the hardware resources are released for further use.

Figure 4 shows a sequence diagram of the process of building a part of the composite skill BT, shown in Figure 1, by the actors D-MAS. The process starts by spawning an AI-holon of the required task with the address of a corresponding AT-holon. The AI-holon gets the task in the form of the required effect of the skill, which can be represented as the BT condition, as described in section 3. To save space, we have omitted the capability matching process by the exploration D-MAS, as it is out of the paper scope. After the resource candidates have been found, the intention agents must allocate the resources for the future execution, analog to [18] (Intention D-MAS in Figure 4. This is done by spawning the RI-actors by the RI-holons. After the RI-holon receives the confirmation that the respective RI-holons have committed to allocate their atomic skills, the skill's coordination logic, defined by the BT's control nodes, must be regenerated. In this case, it is a *Fallback* AI-actor, which controls two atomic skills (see Skill_1 and Skill_2 in Figure 1). The communication channel between the actors is created by the Connector-actor. After all the connections are established, the composite skill presented by the AI-holon is ready for execution, which is shown in the lower part of the Figure 4. The execution is mediated by the BTSync protocol [3], where the Connector-actor serves as a router of the control and feedback signals between the actors.

5 Discussion and Conclusion

In this paper, we have investigated the integration of the skills' composition framework based on BTs with the ARTI holonic architecture, with the focus on the modular RCCPMs. Though the paper is still conceptual and does not yet provide many implementation details and results, it proposes a unifying view on the skill-based approaches and the holonic design of the control software. The main findings are the following.

The skill-based approach focuses more on the system's functional decomposition, which, when applied properly, can be a powerful method of dealing with the system's complexity. It enables one to concentrate on the required functionalities and their orchestration. Their implementation is not relevant as long as it complies with the defined interfaces and behaviors. Nevertheless, this approach may lead to centralized architectures. For example, the orchestration-based approaches are modular but may have challenges with scalability and adaptation to changing reality, as functions do not always directly correspond to objects in the world-of-interest. The holonic ARTI architecture, on the other hand, follows the structural decomposition approach, which mirrors the world-of-interest and scales well with the corresponding reality [18]. These properties are important for the autonomous reconfigurable systems, which aim to integrate new, previously unknown production modules. As the RCCPMs adjust both their structure and functionality, it is essential that both decomposition approaches are well aligned. This work shows how they can complement each other. Skills-oriented design describes machines' functionalities with abstract capabilities and enables their comparison based on what is required and what is currently available. It also standardizes the interfaces to these functionalities in the form of skills. Applied to the ARTI-based MES, this approach can be used by holons for finding the required resources and integrating new functionalities. The flexibility of the ARTI's heterarchical architecture enables automatic functional reconfiguration and paves the way to future autonomously adaptable systems.

Modeling and executing skills using BTs provide additional advantages. Given that BTs and holons share a self-similar and recursive structure, it is possible to seamlessly integrate the two concepts. A distributed BT effectively overlays a network of the holons' actors and enforces a logical hierarchy in the coalition. This allows us to combine the effectiveness of hierarchical control structures with the adaptability and flexibility of heterarchical designs. As the BTs tree structure is easily understandable by humans, this increases transparency of the decisions made in the distributed control systems. Using BTs for the actor's coalition formation addresses the problem of multiresource allocation in ARTI systems, as the RI-holons' actors of the BT effectively allocate their corresponding resources.

The holons, intelligent beings and agents, as defined in the ARTI, build up the layer of intelligence for RCCPMS. The RCCPM's architecture is fractal and consists of all the ARTI holons. The complex and low-level functionality is

Figure 4: Sequence diagram of the skill's composition by the actor D-MAS.

encapsulated in the self-sufficient atomic skills with the standard interface, which are then provided to the system by the respective RI-holons and described by the RT-holons. Once a composite skill is constructed, it can be considered stable, or *atomic*, from the outside for the configuration of the current RCPPM. The resulting control architecture is modular, semi-heterarchical, self-similar, and allows rapid changes of the control software during (re-)configuration of the production modules. It provides a base operational layer for skills and enables further developments towards self-reconfigurable and adaptable CPPMs.

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References

- [1] Luis Ribeiro. *System Design and Implementation Principles for Industry 4.0 - Development of Cyber-Physical Production Systems*. 03 2020.
- [2] Kirill Dorofeev. *Skill-Based Engineering in the Industrial Automation Domain*. PhD thesis, University Linz.
- [3] Aleksandr Sidorenko, Achim Wagner, and Martin Ruskowski. Skills composition framework for reconfigurable cyber-physical production modules. In *2024 IEEE 29th International Conference on Emerging Technologies and Factory Automation (ETFA)*, pages 1–8, 2024.
- [4] Roman Froschauer et al. Capabilities and skills in manufacturing: A survey over the last decade of etfa. In *2022 IEEE 27th International Conference on Emerging Technologies and Factory Automation (ETFA)*, pages 1–8, 2022.
- [5] Aljosha Köcher et al. A reference model for common understanding of capabilities and skills in manufacturing. *at - Automatisierungstechnik*, 71(2):94–104, February 2023.
- [6] M. Volkmann et al. Integration of a feasibility and context check into an OPC UA skill. *IFAC-PapersOnLine*, 54(1):276–281, 2021.
- [7] Patrick Zimmermann et al. Skill-based engineering and control on field-device-level with OPC UA. In *Proceedings of the IEEE international conference on emerging technologies and factory automation (ETFA)*, September 2019.
- [8] Christian Schlegel. *Navigation and Execution for Mobile Robots in Dynamic Environments An Integrated Approach*. PhD thesis, Universitaet Ulm.
- [9] Francesco Rovida et al. Skiros — a skill-based robot control platform on top of ros. In Anis Koubaa, editor, *Robot Operating System (ROS)*, volume 707, pages 121–160. Springer International Publishing, Cham, 2017.
- [10] Michele Colledanchise and Petter Ogren. How behavior trees modularize hybrid control systems and generalize sequential behavior compositions, the subsumption architecture, and decision trees. *IEEE Transactions on Robotics*, 33(2):372–389, April 2017. Publisher: Institute of Electrical and Electronics Engineers Inc.
- [11] Matteo Iovino et al. A survey of behavior trees in robotics and ai. *Robotics and Autonomous Systems*, 154:104096, 2022.
- [12] Schulz-Rosengarten et al. Behavior trees with dataflow: Coordinating reactive tasks in lingua franca. In *Proceedings of the 2024 IEEE/ACM 46th International Conference on Software Engineering: Companion Proceedings, ICSE-Companion '24*, page 304–305, New York, NY, USA, 2024. Association for Computing Machinery.
- [13] Aleksandr Sidorenko et al. Towards using behavior trees in industrial automation controllers. *Procedia CIRP*, 130:1234–1243, 2024. 57th CIRP Conference on Manufacturing Systems 2024 (CMS 2024).
- [14] Paulo Leitão and Francisco Restivo. ADACOR: A holonic architecture for agile and adaptive manufacturing control. *57(2):121–130*.
- [15] Simon Jungbluth et al. Dynamic Replanning using Multi-Agent Systems and Asset Administration Shells. In *2022 IEEE 27th International Conference on Emerging Technologies and Factory Automation (ETFA)*, pages 1–8, 2022.
- [16] Aleksandr Sidorenko et al. The MAS4AI framework for human-centered agile and smart manufacturing. 6.

¹<https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101120218>

²<https://www.smartfactory.de/2022-production-level-4-oekosystem/>

- [17] Alexis T. Bernhard et al. I4.0 holonic multi-agent testbed enabling shared production. In John Soldatos, editor, *Artificial Intelligence in Manufacturing*, pages 231–250. Springer Nature Switzerland.
- [18] Paul Valckenaers and Hendrik Van Brussel. *Design for the unexpected : from holonic manufacturing systems towards a humane mechatronics society*. Elsevier, Oxford, 1st ed. edition, 2016.
- [19] Michele Colledanchise et al. Towards Blended Reactive Planning and Acting using Behavior Trees. In *2019 International Conference on Robotics and Automation (ICRA)*, pages 8839–8845, May 2019. ISSN: 2577-087X.
- [20] Johannes Reich. Composition, cooperation, and coordination of computational systems, February 2021. arXiv:1602.07065 [cs].
- [21] Aleksandr Sidorenko et al. Using Behavior Trees for Coordination of Skills in Modular Reconfigurable CPPMs. In *2022 IEEE 27th International Conference on Emerging Technologies and Factory Automation (ETFA)*, pages 1–8, September 2022.
- [22] Paul Valckenaers. Perspective on holonic manufacturing systems: PROSA becomes ARTI. 120:103226.
- [23] Edward A. Lee, Stephen Neuendorffer, and Michael J. Wirthlin. Actor-Oriented Design of Embedded Hardware and Software Systems. *Journal of Circuits, Systems and Computers*, 12(03):231–260, June 2003.